

Extreme Rainfall Analysis for Urban Vadodara

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Abstract

Vadodara, the industrial and educational hub of western India, is the third largest city of Gujarat. The study deals with rainfall, rainy days and extreme rainfall events during South West monsoon (June to September) observed in Vadodara from 1961 to 2016. The threshold value for extreme rainfall event is taken as one day rainfall crossing 74.73 mm, 95th percentile of daily rainfall record of the study period which happened for 132 times in 56 years out of which 45 events were observed in the month of July. Extreme events were examined at 5 years time window shows highest 18 events during 2001-2005. Sub monthly analysis reveals that the highest 19 extreme events occurred during first 10 days of July. Not only Frequency but magnitude of events also increased, the average annual contribution to annual total rainfall by extreme rainfall is reached to 33% per year after 1996 which was 24% in previous years. Total 11 very heavy rainfall events with the magnitude of 24 hours rainfall above 124.5 mm were observed between 1961-1990 where as 29 very heavy rainfall events were observed during 1991-2016. This study will be helpful for micro-planning and mitigation strategies for disaster management during urban floods due to extreme rainfall.

Keywords: Climate Change, Extreme Rainfall, Statistical and Probabilistic applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

United Nation's goal of sustainable cities and communities is very essential as 55 Percent of human populations will be a part of urban settlement by 2030 (United Nations & Division, 2018). This goal can be achieved not only by creating infrastructure or providing social and economical growth opportunities, but mitigation of changing climate will also play a key role. Cities across the globe are facing an everincreasing variety of challenges of climate vulnerabilities like flooding, cyclones and draught (Gu, et al., 2015) which should be addressed carefully.

A changing climate leads to changes in the frequency, intensity, spatial extent, duration, and timing of extreme weather and climate events, and can result in unprecedented extreme weather and climate events. (Murray & Ebi, 2012). IPCC report (Pachauri, et al., 2014) also confirmed that changes in many extreme weather and climate events have been observed since about 1950. Some of these changes have been linked to human influences, including an increase in the number of heavy precipitation events in a number of regions.

Precipitation is a key indicator changing climate; therefore, appropriate assessment of the urban environment's (land use, aerosols, thermal properties etc.) impact on precipitation will be increasingly important in the field of climate diagnostics and prediction. (Shepherd, 2005).

Huff (Huff & Changnon Jr, 1973) observed that the increase of urban precipitation is related to city size, industrial nuclei generation, and urban thermal effects. The changes have considerable applications related to urban design, local area forecasting, local water supplies, agricultural production and hydrologic design.

Kishtawal (Kishtawal, et al., 2010) observed increasing trend in the frequency of heavy rainfall events over Indian monsoon region is more likely to be over regions where the pace of urbanization is faster. According to Vital, (Vital, et al., 2013) the extreme rainfall in most of urban areas of India show increasing trend and

changed pattern as India underwent high urbanization during 1971-1981. Shastri (Shastri, et al., 2015) found significant impacts of urbanization on extreme rainfall in central and western regions of India during 1979–2007.

2. STUDY AREA

The city of Vadodara is located at western part of India (Latitude: 22 deg 17' 59'' North Longitude: 73 deg 15' 18'' East), situated at an altitude 35.5 m. above mean sea level on the banks of river Vishvamitri in Gujarat state. The city has a relatively flat terrain with the ground sloping from northeast to southwest in a mild manner.

Figure 1 Vadodara city (Study Area)

Since the times of Gaekwar rulers, (1880) city has prominent place in the western part of India. Vadodara faced rapid change after 1970 due to industrial growth particularly in petrochemical, textile and pharmaceutical sectors. The third largest city of Gujarat state is on the golden quadrilateral road with tremendous scope of development. Population of Vadodara is 1.6 million as per 2011 census. The area under Vadodara Municipal boundary is around 159 square kilometers.

Climate of the Vadodara city is characterized by hot and arid from Southwest Monsoon season Dry throughout the year as it falls under semi arid zone. Average annual Rainfall is 806 mm which is majorly during the southwest monsoon season. Average annual Rainy days are 37. Average annual maximum temperature is 34.4 °C and average annual minimum temperature is 21.3 °C.

3. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Objective of the study is to find the temporal pattern of extreme daily rainfall of Vadodara over the study period which may be useful in micro planning for disaster management.

Data of daily rainfall of Vadodara station for data length 1961-2016 is collected from State Water Data Centre (SWDC) Gandhinagar.

Extreme rainfall can be defined as one day rainfall crossing distinct threshold value. The threshold value may be some fixed value defined by some weather monitoring agencies like India Meteorological Department (IMD), according to which if the rainfall of the day is 64.5 mm or more can be defined as heavy rainfall day. This includes very heavy (i.e. 124.5 mm to 244.5 mm) and extremely heavy (i.e. greater than 244.5 mm) rainfall cases (Guhathakurta, et al., 2010) or it can be defined as extreme percentile value of the data like 90th, 95th or 99th percentile of available daily rainfall data.(Sen Roy & Balling, 2004)

The value of 95th percentile of the nonzero daily rainfall for the entire study period of 56 years was determined. The value comes 74.73 mm for the present analysis. Daily rainfall crossing this threshold value is defined as extreme rainfall and the day is considered as a single extreme rainfall event.

Extreme rainfall event has minimum limiting value as defined by threshold rainfall but the magnitude of each rainfall event is different and it is obviously equal to or more than threshold value. Pattern of very heavy rainfall event, one day rainfall greater than 124.5 mm as defined by IMD, is also analyzed for Vadodara city.

Occurrence of extreme event in each month is also analyzed with five year time window to detect the change over the study period. Monthly and sub monthly occurrence of total extreme events gives clear information regarding extreme events occurred in 10 days time interval.

Contribution of extreme rainfall to total annual rainfall (%) is a measure of effect of magnitude of extreme rainfall on annual rainfall. The contribution of extreme rainfall is calculated for each year.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Extreme rainfall for the month of June varies from 75 mm (21st June 2007) to 238 mm (29th June 2005). July extreme rainfall varies from 75 mm (3rd July 1978) to 315 mm (1st July 2005). Extreme rainfall for the month of August ranges from 75.8 mm (10th August 1979) to 224 mm (17th August 1978). The same for September observed with minimum value of 75 mm (16th September 1998) to maximum value of 256 mm (11th September 1994). It is to be noted that maximum value of extreme rainfall for all months except August was recorded after 1990 (Fig-2).

It is also observed from figure (Fig-2) that rainfall events with very heavy magnitude (greater than 124.5 mm according to IMD) have increased for all the months of monsoon after 1990. Only 2 very heavy rainfall events took place in June before 1990 which increased to 5 events in remaining 26 years. Number of very heavy rainfall events of July increased from 3 to 10. Similarly, month of August and September observed jump from 4 and 2 events, before 1990, to 8 and 6 very heavy rainfall events respectively after 1990. It is clear from figure (Fig-2) that 11 very heavy rainfall events were observed before 1990 while 29 very heavy rainfall events were observed during 1991-2016. Similar analysis shows that 65 extreme events occurred during 1961-1990 while 67 events occurred during 1991-2016.

Total 132 extreme events were observed during the study period of 1961-2016. Highest number of extreme events, 45 events occurred in the month of July, followed by the month of August which recorded 44 events. (Fig-3) Starting and ending months of monsoon i.e. June and September have recorded 24 and 19 extreme events respectively.

Figure 2 Month wise Extreme Rainfall Events, Vadodara

Figure 3 Month wise total extreme events, Vadodara

Extreme events were classified in the subsets of 10 days interval in sub monthly analysis. (Fig-4) Highest, 19 events recorded during 1st to 10th July while lowest, 2 events were recorded during 11 to 20 June. The last 10 days i.e. 21-30th June have observed 17 extreme events. Sub monthly analysis of August shows that each subset of 10 days recorded at least 14 extreme events. 16 extreme events were observed during 21st -31st August. The first subset of September (1-10) recorded 10 extreme events while the third subset (21-30) recorded only 3 extreme events over the study period.

Figure 4 Sub monthly Extreme Events Analysis, Vadodara

Contribution of total extreme rainfall to total annual rainfall is increasing after 1996 (Fig-5). Even when total annual rainfall was less than 400 in the years 1999 and 2000, the extreme rainfall contributed more than 20% to annual rainfall. Average annual contribution by extreme rainfall was 24.19% before 1996 which rose to 33.6%. 1364 mm rainfall was recorded during extreme rainy days in 2005 where total annual rainfall was observed 1986 mm. Unprecedented 68% contribution by extreme rainfall to total annual rainfall was observed in 2005.

Figure 5 Contribution of Extreme Rainfall to Total Annual Rainfall

Total extreme events occurred in each month during whole study period were classified in five years time window. (Fig-6) The month of June shows highest 6 extreme events during 2001-2005 which is one fourth of total extreme events observed in the month of June during entire study period. (Fig-6a).

As discussed earlier, the highest number of extreme events was observed in the month of July. It is to be noted that the last two time windows of 2006-2010 and 2011-2016 show 7 extreme events each (Fig-6b). It clearly indicates that the extreme events in the last decade were increased unprecedentedly and play vital role in the rise of total extreme events of July.

Except the five year time window of 1996-2000, the month of August shows at least 2 extreme events in each time window. There were (Fig-6c) 8 extreme events observed during the period 2001-2005, which is highest for all the months in single time window.

It is interesting to see the change in extreme events of the month of the September. No extreme event was observed during 15-year time period between 1971-1985. (Fig-6d) At least 1 extreme event was observed in each time window after 1996. It shows overall increasing tendency. Highest 5 extreme events were observed in the last time window of 2011-2016. It can be considered as an indicator of change in climate and rainfall pattern with further analysis.

Figure 6 Sub Decadal Extreme Rainfall Events (1961-2016) (a) June (b) July (c) August (d) September

4. CONCLUSIONS

The value of 95th percentile of the nonzero daily rainfall for the entire study period of 56 years was determined. The value comes 74.73 mm for the present analysis. Total 132 extreme events were observed during the study period of 1961-2016. Highest number of extreme events, 45 events occurred in the month of July.

Sub monthly analysis shows that the highest events (19) were recorded during 1st to 10th July while lowest events (2) were recorded during 11 to 20 June for entire study period.

Total extreme events occurred in each month during whole study period were classified in five years time window. The last two time windows of 2006-2010 and 2011-2016 show 7 extreme events each for July. It clearly indicates that the extreme events in the last decade were increased unprecedentedly. 8 extreme events were observed in the month of August during 2001-2005, which is the highest for all the months in single time window. Highest 5 extreme events were observed for the month of September in the last time window of 2011-2016.

Total 11 very heavy rainfall events with the magnitude of 24 hours rainfall above 124.5 mm were observed between 1961-1990 where as 29 very heavy rainfall events were observed during 1991-2016.

Contribution of total extreme rainfall to total annual rainfall is increasing after 1996. Unprecedented 68% contribution by extreme rainfall to total annual rainfall was observed in 2005.

The analysis of extreme rainfall events shows the increasing trend with unprecedented frequency and magnitude in recent years, which can be considered as an indicator of climate change. The present analysis can be utilized in planning of infrastructure and disaster management for Vadodara city.

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